
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE RATIO AND CONSTRAINT EQUATION AND CALCULUS

A PREPRINT

Wu, Xinjian

May 14, 2025

ABSTRACT

Through the analysis of the ratio in the difference between two Ratio and Constraint equations, the connection between the Ratio and Constraint equation and calculus is further established Wu [2025] .

Keywords Ratio and Constraint Equation · Calculus

1 Main

For Two Recurrence Relations, $\frac{a_{n+k}}{a_n} = T(k, (a_{n+i})_{i=0}^{k-1})$ and $b_{n+k} = b_n + k$.

Let $k = 1$ and $a_n = b_n$, $\frac{T_a^1 - 1}{T_b^1 - 1} = \frac{\frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{a_n}}{\frac{b_{n+1} - b_n}{b_n}} = \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{1}$.

Introducing differentials, evidently, this leads to derivatives.

References

Xinjian Wu. Towards a general analytical method for convergence analysis of recursive processes. 1(1):2, 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.15253610.